

crosses were evaluated. We placed 2-g leaf blades from each plant in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution according to the method of Sood and Siddiq. Samples

were smelled and evaluated for aroma after 10 min.

F₁ plants from all the reciprocal crosses were nonaromatic, indicating that

a recessive nuclear gene controls aroma in Jin-Long Dao and 80-66. The F₂ plant scent evaluation indicated a 3:1 (non-aroma:aroma) segregation (see table). □

Breeding methods

Heterosis and inbreeding depression in rice

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Ten divergent parents—Mahsuri, Adamchini, IET4140, IET7562, Kanakjeera, IR50, IR52, Dhaneswar, Pawanpeer, and TAU18—were crossed in all possible combinations, excluding reciprocals, to study the extent of heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and inbreeding depression for yield and yield components.

Parents and their 45 F₁ and 45 F₂ were grown in a completely randomized block design, with three replications. Plants were spaced at 20 × 15 cm, with one row of 20 plants for parents and F₁ and six rows of 20 plants for F₂. Observations were recorded for 10 randomly selected plants from parents and F₁, and 50 plants from F₂.

The genotypic correlation coefficient indicated that grain yield was positively and significantly correlated with number of effective tillers/plant ($r = 0.38$) and number of grains/panicle ($r = 0.45$). Other characters, such as days to panicle emergence, plant height, panicle length, and 100-grain weight, showed either negative or nonsignificant positive correlations with yield.

The cross combinations exhibiting more than 20% heterobeltiosis for grain yield are in the table. Crosses showing more than 40% heterobeltiosis for grain yield were Kanakjeer/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET4140/TAU 18, Adamchini/TAU 18, Adamchini/Pawanpeer, Adamchini/IET7562, and Adamchini/IR50. Crosses showing better negative heterobeltiosis for days to panicle emergence were Adamchini/IET7562 and Adamchini/IR50, IET7562/IR52; for plant height, they were Adamchini/IET7562, Adamchini/Pawanpeer, Adamchini/IR50, IET4140/TAU18, and Kanakjeera/IR52.

Only 11 of 54 crosses showed positive significant heterobeltiosis for number of effective tillers/plant. Crosses with appreciable heterobeltiosis were Mahsuri/Kanakjeera, IET4140/IR52, and IR50/Pawanpeer.

The crosses with high heterobeltiosis for grains/panicle were IET4140/TAU 18, IET4140/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET7562/IR52, IET4140/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET7562/IR52, and IET7562/TAU18. The crosses Mahsuri/IET4140 and IET7562/IR50 expressed better heterobeltiosis for 100-grain weight.

Out of 45 crosses, 31 showed significant inbreeding depression for plant height, 32 for days to panicle emergence, 41 for panicle length, 42 for tillers/plant, 31 for grains/panicle, 41 for 100-grain weight, and 42 for grain yield. Some crosses had high heterosis with high inbreeding depression, some showed more heterosis and medium inbreeding depression, and some had high heterosis with low inbreeding depression. □

Heterobeltiosis and inbreeding depression for yield and its components in promising hybrids. ^a

Cross	Days to panicle emergence		Plant height (cm)		Effective tillers/plant (no.)		Grains/panicle (no.)		Grain yield/plant	
	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)
Mahsuri/IET7562	-14.5**	-6.3**	3.9**	1.0	-9.0	20.2**	-30.7**	30.4**	34.9**	50.8**
Mahsuri/Kanakjeera	0.1	5.4**	3.8**	13.6**	31.6**	41.1**	-36.7**	26.2**	44.7**	61.7**
Mahsuri/Pawanpeer	-4.3**	13.9**	-1.9	-9.8**	11.3**	49.9**	-36.8**	35.5**	34.3**	56.6**
Mahsuri/TAU18	-7.0**	-2.8*	-2.1	8.8**	-6.5	23.0**	-19.9**	32.8**	20.7**	38.3**
Adamchini/IET7562	-24.6**	-11.9**	-27.7**	-9.2**	-19.0**	32.6**	14.9**	34.0**	54.6**	55.5**
Adamchini/IR50	-17.3**	4.7**	-13.6**	4.4**	-9.3	0.4	-11.2**	2.1	45.0**	22.2**
Adamchini/Pawanpeer	-10.5**	5.7**	-22.7**	15.3**	0.2	18.3**	-40.0**	9.1**	57.4**	17.6**
Adamchini/TAU18	-6.9**	5.3**	7.6**	7.4**	13.4**	26.8**	-9.2**	6.9**	57.5**	28.4**
IET4140/Kanakjeera	-0.1	3.1	-12.9**	9.1**	-5.6	17.1**	38.2**	-52.4**	28.4**	20.9**
IET4140/IR50	4.0**	11.5**	-2.8*	-30.3**	-42.3**	0.5	46.0**	11.3**	41.7**	13.3**
IET4140/IR52	14.1**	5.0**	1.4	10.0**	33.1**	11.1**	-6.4**	8.4**	20.7**	39.7**
IET4140/Pawanpeer	-0.2	2.4*	2.7	12.2**	12.5**	26.1**	14.9**	4.1*	20.4**	15.0**
IET4140/TAU18	0.8	1.4	-15.5**	2.6	2.7	10.7	52.1**	21.4**	70.4**	23.7**
IET7562/Pawanpeer	0.2	2.0	19.0**	1.5	-3.3	31.0**	3.1*	16.3**	34.0**	55.9**
Kanakjeera/IR50	2.2*	6.2**	-1.4	19.6**	-14.9**	18.8**	-15.5**	7.5**	160.4**	50.4**
Kanakjeera/TAU18	3.9**	3.8**	6.4**	6.1	-17.2**	5.2	17.2**	28.6**	33.8**	37.2**
IR50/Pawanpeer	-0.7	7.7**	24.5**	11.6**	22.8**	29.8**	61.3**	44.7**	98.7**	61.1**
IR50/TAU18	-4.1**	-1.5	-15.1**	-3.0*	-1.3	33.7**	-3.2*	5.2**	24.1**	16.3**
Pawanpeer/TAU18	7.3**	6.4**	-5.7**	10.2**	-10.5	13.4*	-0.0	6.2**	35.2**	29.8**
SE	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.5	0.6	0.4	2.4	2.5	1.1	0.8

^a * = significance at P = 5%. ** = significance at P = 1%. HBT = heterobeltiosis, ID = inbreeding depression

Zinc increases rate of twin seedlings of rice

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We studied how Zn affected the rate of twin seedlings in polyembryonic rice varieties: *indica* Shuang 3 and Shuang 13, and *japonica* Lu 52.

Three hundred dehulled seeds per treatment were soaked in different concentrations of Zn²⁺ (ZnSO₄) solution at 37°C for 1 d. The check was soaked in distilled water. The seeds were then sterilized in 0.1% mercuric chloride for 10 min and placed in the same solution at 25°C to hasten germination. Twin seedling rates were calculated 4 d later.

Effects of Zn²⁺ concentrations on rate^a of twin seedlings germination percentage^b in 3 varieties.

Zn ²⁺ concn (M)	Shuang 3 (indica)		Shuang 13 (indica)		Lu 52 (japonica)	
	Twin seedling rate (%)	Germination (%)	Twin seedling rate (%)	Germination (%)	Twin seedling rate (%)	Germination (%)
Control	30.9	90.3	3.3	81.0	4.5	72.9
1 × 10 ⁻⁶	33.2	82.3	6.6	80.7	5.4	77.2
1 × 10 ⁻⁵	41.8	90.1	6.8	77.8	7.0	76.0
1 × 10 ⁻⁴	34.7	90.7	6.0	82.1	5.9	77.8
1 × 10 ⁻³	31.4	87.9	4.5	86.6	5.1	80.6
1 × 10 ⁻²	34.0	92.7	5.0	74.3	6.1	72.3
1 × 10 ⁻¹	0	0	0	0	0	0

^aNumber of twin seedlings (including triplets) ÷ no. of total seeds × 100. ^b(Number of twin seedlings + no. of single seedlings) ÷ no. of total seeds × 100.

The optimum concentration of Zn²⁺ was 1 × 10⁻⁵ M, at which the twin seedlings frequency of Shuang 3 increased by 10.9%. The twin seedling rate of Shuang 13 increased by 3.5% and that of Lu 52, 2.5% (see table). The results also indicated that Zn²⁺ concentrations of 1 × 10⁻¹ M restricted seedling development.

Zn²⁺ increases the twin seedling rate because it is related to the synthesis of IAA and protein and stimulates N metabolism. □

Restorers and maintainers for five CMS lines

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Isolation of restorers and maintainers for different cytoplasmic-genetic male sterile (CMS) lines is important to develop appropriate hybrid combinations and new CMS lines for hybrid rice breeding programs.

Twenty-one locally adapted, high-yielding elite breeding lines were used as pollen parents for crossing five CMS lines developed at CRRRI (Kiran A,

Krishna A, Deepa A, Madhuri A [WA source], and Krishna A [Kalinga-I source]). We randomly collected anthers from 10-15 spikelets of three panicles from individual F₁ plants during anthesis. They were examined under a microscope using Lugol's iodine solution; pollen sterility was estimated. Spikelet fertility was estimated on two to three panicles that had been bagged on each of the hybrid plants.

Varieties were classified as effective restorers (spikelet fertility more than 80%), partial restorer (spikelet fertility 25-79%), weak maintainers (spikelet fertility less than 25%), and effective

maintainers (spikelet fertility less than 1%).

We found most of the varieties to be partial restorers for the CMS lines of wild abortive (WA) and Kalinga I cytoplasmic sources. Aswathi, Punjab Basmati, and Ratna were found to be effective maintainers for Krishna A (Kalinga I); Aswathi, an effective restorer for Krishna A (WA); and Ratna, a partial restorer for Kiran A, Krishna A, Deepa A, and Madhuri A (WA).

Varieties IR9828-91-2-3 and Mahsuri were found to be effective restorers for 4 WA CMS lines (Kiran A, Madhuri A, Krishna A, or Deepa A) while they were partial restorers for Krishna A (Kalinga I) (see table). Like IR9828-91-2-3 and Mahsuri, Tetep was an effective restorer for Deepa A (WA), but a partial restorer for Krishna A (Kalinga I).

The variety Kalinga I was an effective restorer for CMS lines Krishna A (WA), Deepa A (WA), Madhuri A (WA), and Krishna A (Kalinga I) and a partial restorer for CMS line Kiran A (WA).

These findings indicate that the cytoplasm of Krishna A (Kalinga I source) may be different from that of Krishna A (WA) and other CMS lines of WA source. The behavior of a few varieties for the CMS lines from the same cytoplasmic source (WA) was sometimes different, possibly because of the nuclear and cytoplasmic interaction between the varieties and the CMS lines or the heterozygosity of the pollen parents. □

Restorer or maintainer reaction of elite lines in crosses with 5 CMS lines possessing WA and Kalinga I cytoplasm, 1991 dry season.^a

Male parent	Reaction of elite lines				
	Kiran A (WA)	Krishna A (WA)	Deepa A (WA)	Madhuri A (WA)	Krishna A (Kalinga I)
Annapurna	PR	PR	PR	PR	PR
ARC5961	-	-	-	-	PR
Archana	PR	-	-	-	-
Aswathi	-	R	-	-	M
Bhavani	-	-	-	-	WM
CR142-38	PR	PR	-	-	PR
CR386-9-3	-	-	-	WM	-
IR36	-	-	-	-	PR
IR9828-91-2-3	-	R	-	R	PR
Kalinga I	PR	R	R	R	R
Kranti	PR	-	-	-	PR
Kumar	-	-	-	R	-
Mahsuri	R	-	R	R	PR
Pokkali	PR	-	PR	PR	-
Ptb 10	-	-	-	-	WM
Punjab Basmati	-	-	-	-	M
Prakash	-	-	-	-	PR
Prasad	PR	-	-	-	-
Ratna	PR	PR	PR	PR	M
Tetep	-	-	R	-	PR
Vijaya	WM	PR	-	-	-

^aR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, WM = weak maintainer, and M = maintainer.